

Prediction of operator intentions by action forecasting in collaborative assembly tasks

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I. INTRODUCTION

The logic of Industry 4.0 foresees humans and robots as indistinguishable parts of a larger heterogeneous body of distributed autonomous and cooperative entities. Under such a perspective, robots are endowed with self and environment awareness and are able to smartly interact with both humans and other machines [1]. Consequently, and in contrast to the third industrial revolution, machines are not intended to substitute humans in industry, but to work with them in synergy.

In collaborative industrial scenarios, safety greatly depends on the reciprocal understanding between the human operator and the robotic system. On the one hand, the operator needs to be aware of the collaborative robot's motion to guarantee him or her own safety. On the other, the robot must identify, understand and forecast operator's actions to promptly react and safely adapt to either expected or unexpected operative conditions. Under the assumption that operator's intentions are mainly focused on completing the assigned task, such intentions can be predicted in terms of the sequence of actions required to complete it. Therefore, intentions forecasting greatly relies on the ability of the robotic system to promptly identify tasks executed by the operator and to model the transitions between them. Moreover, beyond normal operative conditions, it is of fundamental regard to identify unexpected operator's actions to avoid any dangerous circumstance.

II. PROBLEM UNDER STUDY

In industrial assembly scenarios, the problem of tasks prediction is greatly simplified by the cyclical nature of the operator's work. Therefore, the prediction of intentions problem can be analyzed in terms of three distinct processes: action *anticipation*, action *forecasting* and *collaborative* behavior.

Action anticipation refers to the prompt recognition or identification of the current task executed by the operator. This process is continuously executed, such as to monitor the operator's actions on real-time. The action identification can be driven by different cues, like gestures (expressive and

meaningful body poses and motions), scene objects being manipulated, environmental information, etc. For example, Koppula et al. [2] show how the link between human actions and object affordances can be exploited to anticipate human intentions. Also, in [3], the authors predict grasping gestures using an eye-tracker device and wearable attached to the user's hand. Casalino et al. [4] propose a framework for the prediction of human intentions from RGB-D data while improving the human awareness by means of haptic feedback.

Action forecasting comprises the total or partial reconstruction of the assembly cycle state and, thus, also the prediction of future actions. Consequently, this process implies the generation and constant refinement of an action transition model. Such a model can be used not only to predict future actions, but also to validate the outcomes of the anticipation process. The latter validation allows to identify and safely react to unexpected operator's actions. In this context, Zanchettin et al. [5] describe a framework to infer the most likely reaching target of the operator's hand based on RGB-D measurements. In [6] a method to predict future action patterns is described. The method allows to forecast when a specific collaborative operation will be requested by the operator.

The robot's collaborative behavior is achieved by dynamically allocating its tasks, in terms of the action transition model provided by the action forecasting process. In other words, the robot behavior is driven by situational awareness of the assembly process. Although robot behavior adaptation has been widely studied in the robotics community [7], the advances on machine learning techniques are allowing a widespread application in industrial contexts [8], [9].

III. RELATED WORK

Beyond our manufacturing applicative context, action anticipation based on human activities has been widely considered in literature [10], [11]. We investigate three methodologies, which are respectively based on convolutional neural networks (CNN) [12], [13], recurrent neural networks (RNN) [14] and reinforced encoder-decoder networks (RED) [15].

Rodriguez et al. [12] propose a CNN to generate a single motion image for each video sequence under study to perform future actions predictions. The motion is captured using dynamic images [16], which encodes the appearance's temporal evolution of a small set of consecutive frames into a single one. These images are constructed using the rank pooling method [17]. The motion prediction is obtained by means of a generative model [18].

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Singh et al. [13] jointly evaluate spatio-temporal action localization and prediction via a single shot multi-box detector (SSD). The SSD CNNs performs the regression and classification of the boxes in each video frame potentially containing an action of interest. At prediction time, the SSD network generates scores for the presence of each object category in each default box and produces adjustments to the box to better match the object shape.

In [14], the authors propose a RNN with a radial basis function kernel (RBF) to improve the performance of feature mapping for the anticipation task. This allows the feature mapping, based only on a small number of the earliest frames of a video, to generate future features with a small portion of the parameters required by traditional RNN. The action prediction is based on a simple multilayer perceptron feeded with the aforementioned future features.

In contrast to the previously described solutions, based on past frame's representations, Gao et al. [15] proposed an action prediction model that exploits the whole history trend. The model consists in reinforced encoder-decoder network (RED) which anticipates the next representation of an action using a LSTM [19] network as its basic cell. In RED a reinforcement module is adopted to provide sequence-level supervision.

Action anticipation can be also performed in terms of human pose data. For example, in [20] a non-parametric Bayesian inference method for human action recognition based on motion capture data was proposed. However, nowadays is it possible to exploit human pose measurements extracted from images [21], [22].

IV. RESEARCH SCOPE

Based on previous developments of anticipation and forecasting [23], [24], our aim in this project is to develop an integrated deep model for task prognostic, suitable for inferring operator intentions inside collaborative industrial manufacturing scenarios. Based on the ability to both anticipate and foresee the operator task evolution, it is possible to infer step by step the deployment of a joint dynamic between the robot and the operator. As a consequence, our objective is to effectively allocate the robot's activities so to increase safety and ergonomics, while improving the robot's performance.

Therefore, one major empirical concern is focused on the temporal coherence of subsequent predictions, action anticipation and forecasting timeliness and the responsiveness to unseen or unexpected actions; fundamental aspects for planning safe collaborative robot motions. A second major empirical concern is related to the generation of a reliable dataset and the definition of a trustful performance metric. Specially, when the assumption that the operator's intentions are mainly focused on completing the assigned task doesn't hold, due the stochastic nature of such intentions. This is a critical issue, since it is not possible to clearly define a priori a set of unexpected operator's behaviors without tightly constraining the set of feasible ones. Therefore, the action anticipation and forecasting processes need to be flexible enough to handle a wide range of operator's behavior variations on each executed

action. Which, in practice, may require a large amount of training and testing data.

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